

Mixed Chelate Complexes of Manganese(II)

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Manuscript received 13 October 1977, accepted 21 November 1977

Manganese(III) complexes like manganese *tris*-thiocarbamates, -acetylacetonates and -picolinates were reacted with heterochelates. Even though mixed chelate complexes were formed, surprisingly trivalent manganese was invariably reduced to divalent state. Analytical, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infra red and electronic spectral data reveal that these heterochelate compounds are high spin manganese(II) complexes with presumably tetrahedral configuration.

DITHIOCARBAMATES are well known as Vulcanization accelerators in rubber industry and have also been patented as fungicides. Amongst them, the dithiocarbamates of manganese have been under controversial discussion in recent years. Especially, manganese(II) dithio-carbamates reported earlier¹⁻³ were contradicted^{4,5} due to their ready susceptibility towards oxidation by air. They are reported to be stable only in inert atmosphere and are easily oxidised to manganese(III) in presence of atmospheric air. In case of manganese (III) complexes, attempts were made earlier to prepare some mixed chelate complexes⁶⁻⁸ and study their structures in an environment of heteroatomic ligand field. In none of these complexes dithiocarbamate was present as bonded ligand. In view of this, we tried to prepare some mixed chelate complexes of manganese(III) containing dithiocarbamate and 8-hydroxyquinoline (ox), acetylacetonate (acac) or picolinic acid (pyca). These reactions were found to produce only manganese(II) mixed chelates which was confirmed by analytical data, magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectra. The manganese(III) was found to be invariably reduced to manganese(II) when dithiocarbamate is one of the chelating group.

Experimental

The diethyl (Et_2dtc), piperidyl (Pipdte) and morpholyl (Morphdte) dithiocarbamates of manganese(III) were prepared by known methods^{9,10}. *Tris* (acetylacetonato) manganese(III) was prepared as described by Jacob¹¹.

Preparation of mixed chelate complexes :

$Mn(Et_2dte)(ox)$, $Mn(Pipdte)(ox)$, $Mn(Morphdte)(ox)$

Manganese *tris* thiocarbamates, *viz.* $Mn(Et_2dte)_3$, $Mn(pipdte)_3$ and $Mn(Morphdte)_3$ were reacted separately with 8-hydroxyquinoline (ox) in 1 : 1 molar ratio in acetone medium. The resulting solution was refluxed for nearly 30 mts, when microcrystalline compounds separated out which were suction

filtered, washed with acetone followed by ether and dried in *vacuo*.

$Mn(acac)(Et_2dte)$; $Mn(acac)(Pipdte)$

To a chloroform solution of $Mn(acac)_3$ an ethanolic solution of sodium salt of diethyl or piperidyl dithiocarbamate (1 : 1 molar ratio) was added. Immediately the original dark colour of *tris*-acetylacetonate was discharged and a greyish white silky compound separated out. The contents were refluxed for a few minutes to ensure complete reaction. The separated compound was suction filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in *vacuo*. The same compounds were obtained during the reverse process, when *tris*-dithiocarbamates of manganese(III) were reacted with acetylacetonate in 1 : 1 molar ratio followed by dropwise addition of ammonia.

$Mn(Pyca)(Et_2dte)$, $Mn(Pyca)(Pipdte)$

Tris-picolinatomanganese(III), $Mn(Pyca)_3$, was prepared by reacting methanolic solutions of manganese (III) acetate dihydrate and picolinic acid in 1 : 3 molar ratio. On stirring well a bright orange coloured shining microcrystalline compound separated out which was suction filtered, washed with methanol followed by ether and dried in *vacuo*.

Hot ethanolic solution of $Mn(Pyca)_3$ was treated with ethanolic solution of sodium salt of diethyl or piperidyl dithiocarbamate in 1 : 1 molar ratio and refluxed for one hour and cooled. Shining chatolate coloured compounds separated out which were suction filtered washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in *vacuo*. The same compounds were obtained when *tris*-dithiocarbamates of manganese(III) were refluxed with picolinic acid in 1 : 1 molar ratio for 30 minutes.

Physical measurements :

All the complexes reported have elemental analyses, electrical conductivities, magnetic susceptibilities,

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i.r. spectra and electronic spectra consistent with their formulations and these data are presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3. Manganese and sulphur were estimated by manganese(III) dithiocarbamates are both readily oxidised and reduced to manganese(IV) and manganese(II)¹³. In the present case, the tris-di-

TABLE—1 ANALYTICAL, MELTING POINT, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF MANGANESE(II) COMPLEXES.

Compound	Colour	M.P. (°C)	% Mn Found/Calc.	% S Found/Calc.	Λ^m (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M)
1. Mn(Et ₂ dtc) (ox)	dirty green	> 300	15.69/15.82	18.39/18.45	3.8	5.96
2. Mn(Pipdte) (ox)	dirty green	> 300	14.99/15.30	17.92/17.84	3.6	5.96
3. Mn(Morphdte) (ox)	Greenish yellow	> 300	15.01/15.22	17.6 /17.74	3.9	5.93
4. Mn(acac) (Et ₂ dte)	Greyishwhite	290	18.3 /18.20	21.0 /21.21	3.9	5.80
5. Mn(acac) (Pipdte)	Greyish white	> 300	17.6 /17.51	20.7 /20.44	3.7	5.76
6. Mn(Pyca) (Et ₂ dte)	Shining chocolate	> 300	16.71/16.89	19.53/19.72	3.5	5.85
7. Mn(Pyca) (Pipdte)	Light yellow	> 300	16.15/16.30	19.0 /19.03	3.4	5.79

TABLE—2 INFRARED ABSORPTION BANDS (CM⁻¹) OF MIXED CHELATE MANGANESE(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	dithiocarbamate			Oxine	acetylacetonone		Picolinic acid
	ν (C-N)	ν_{as} (C-S)	ν_{s} (C-S)	ν (C-O)	ν (C-C)	ν (C-O)	ν_{as} (CO-O)
1. Mn(Et ₂ dte) (ox)	1500s	1020w	710s	1095s			
2. Mn(Pipdte) (ox)	1500s	1010s	710s	1097s			
3. Mn(Morphdte) (ox)	1500vs	1010s	710s	1097s			
4. Mn(acac) (Et ₂ dte)	1520s	1000s	700s		1600vs	1520s	
5. Mn(acac) (Pipdte)	1520s	1005s	710s		1600vs	1520s	
6. Mn(Pyca) (Et ₂ dte)	1520w	1002s	738s				1640vs, 1600vs, 1578s
7. Mn(Pyca) (Pipdte)	1510w	1010s	738s				1640s, 1605s, 1580s

s=sharp, vs - very sharp, w = weak.

TABLE—3 ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF MIXED CHELATE MANGANESE(II) COMPLEXES.

Compound	Absorption max. (cm ⁻¹)			
1. Mn(Et ₂ dte) (ox)	26315	23530	22470	20200
2. Mn(Pipdte) (ox)	26315	23570	22990	20000
3. Mn(Morphdte) (ox)	26315	23570	22730	20000
4. Mn(acac) (Et ₂ dte)	27030	23570	22730	20410
5. Mn(acac) (Pipdte)	27030	23530	22470	20000
6. Mn(Pyca) (Et ₂ dte)	27030	23570	22730	20000
7. Mn(Pyca) (Pipdte)	26315	23530	22470	20000

standard methods. The conductance measurements in nitrobenzene medium were carried out using Toshniwal conductivity bridge, type CL 0102 with a dip type cell. The magnetic susceptibility measurements at room temperature were carried out on solid specimens using Guoy method. Infrared spectra in the range 5000-650 cm⁻¹ were recorded on nujol mull using Unicam SP-200 double beam spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded using Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer. Since the compounds were not appreciably soluble in organic solvents, the nujol mull paper technique was used.

Results and Discussion

An important property of the dithiocarbamates as ligands is their capacity for stabilizing metal ions in a wide range of oxidation states. It was reported that

dithiocarbamates were found to undergo reduction to divalent state on the introduction of a heterochelate group in the complex.

All the complexes are non electrolytes as evidenced by low molar conductance values (Table 1) of the 10⁻³M solutions in nitrobenzene medium. Convincing support for the divalent state of manganese in the above complexes is obtained from their magnetic susceptibility values. The dithiocarbamate complexes of manganese(III) have been reported to have magnetic moments in the range 4.4-4.9 B.M.^{13, 14}. But manganese(II) compounds usually have spin-only magnetic moments of ca. 5.9 B.M. (high spin d⁵ configuration, S=5/2) which are temperature independent¹⁵ unless antiferromagnetism is present. The complexes under present investigation give rise to magnetic moment values of 5.76-5.96 B.M. (Table 1) indicating the presence of 5 unpaired electrons which are quite in conformity with a spin-free manganese(II) state. These values of magnetic moment cannot otherwise be explained in terms of manganese(III) (3d⁴ configuration).

Infrared spectra :

The relevant infrared absorption bands due to the coordinated chelates of the complexes with their possible assignments are given in Table 2. Many bands due to 8-hydroxyquinoline and picolinic acid are found to be superimposed over the bands of

dithiocarbamates. However, the most characteristic bands which could be distinctly assigned were given in the table. The ν (C—N) and ν (C—S) bands due to dithiocarbamates indicate clearly that they are coordinated to the metal ion through both the sulphur atoms^{9,10}. The ν (C—O) for 8-hydroxyquinoline (ox) obtained at 1095-1097 cm^{-1} indicates that it is coordinated to the metal ion through nitrogen and oxygen atoms¹⁶. In the acetylacetonato complexes, the bands due to ν (C=C) and ν (C=O) were obtained at 1600 and 1520 cm^{-1} , respectively as expected, indicating the presence of coordinated acetyl acetone group¹⁷. In case of picolinic acid complexes, the band due to free carboxyl group at 1710 cm^{-1} was found to be absent. Other bands due to ν_{as} (COO) and pyridine ring were found to be present as observed by Fowles *et al.*¹⁸. This suggests that picolinic acid is coordinated to the metal ion through oxygen and nitrogen atoms.

Electronic Spectra :

The dithiocarbamate complexes of manganese (III) are found to give bands⁹ at ~ 27800 , ~ 20000 and ~ 16000 cm^{-1} . In the complexes now studied, no band at ~ 16000 cm^{-1} could be obtained which indicates the absence of manganese(III) species in the complexes. On the other hand, all the absorption bands recorded for the present complexes (Table 3), can be satisfactorily assigned on the basis of a tetrahedral geometry for manganese(II). Forster and Goodgame have studied¹⁹ the electronic spectra of $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}]_2[\text{Mn}(\text{NCO})_4]$ and found transitions from ${}^6\text{A}_1$ ground state occurring at *Ca.* 20400 [\rightarrow ${}^4\text{T}_1(\text{G})$], 22400 [\rightarrow ${}^4\text{T}_2(\text{G})$], 23300 [\rightarrow ${}^4\text{E}$, ${}^4\text{A}_1(\text{G})$], 27500 and *Ca.* 26000 cm^{-1} . They have suggested a tetrahedral configuration for the above compound on the basis of their results. The bands obtained in the present investigation are similar and definitely indicate a tetrahedral geometry to all the complexes now reported.

It is therefore interesting to find that even though our efforts to prepare some mixed chelate complexes of trivalent manganese did not succeed, we could characterise mixed chelate complexes of divalent manganese. These are very stable whilst $\text{Mn}(\text{dto})_2$ is susceptible to aerial oxidation.

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